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Recovery of protein and carbohydrate from whey water using integrated membrane processes

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Introduction: Whey is a by-product of cheese production. It contains water (93-94%), lactose (45-50 g/L), proteins (7-9 g/L), minerals (6-8 g/L), vitamins, and milk fat (1-2 g/L) (1). Whey protein is used as food supplements for muscle growth, and as animal fodder. Membrane technology is popular for the recovery of whey protein and carbohydrate. Commercial membranes available for whey water recovery includes, Nadir GmbH (UF-PES), Zoltecc Rt MAVIBRAN (UF-PVDF), Centramate, Pall Germany (UF-PES), Koch Membrane System (UF-PES), RA55 Millipore NF-400 Da, Dow Chemical USA NF-200, Koch membrane TFC-SR3, TIA Bollene France UF NF-NTR7450 (2). This study involves fractionation of whey water, recovery of protein and carbohydrate using an integrated UF-NF system, and effect of hydraulic cleaning of membrane.

Methods: Whey water was filtered through UF membranes (UF-20 kDa and UF-50 kDa) purchased from Tech Inc. Ltd., in a dead-end filtration cell (Tech Inc. Ltd.) at 2 bar (N₂). The UF permeate was passed through NF 200 Da (KOCH membrane MPF-34) at 20 bar NF-cell (Tech Inc. Ltd.). The water flux was determined by measuring permeate volume at different time intervals, protein and carbohydrate concentration in feed and permeate (UF and NF) was analyzed by spectrophotometer (UV-Vis Systronics 119, Kolkata).

Results & Discussions: The UF membrane shows that increased feed pressure (0.5 to 2.5 bar) improves membrane flux. UF-20 resulted increased flux from 17 LMH to 23 LMH, and for UF-50 it increased from 15 LMH to 20 LMH. Similarly at fixed pressure (2 bar) and at different time intervals, the water flux decreased with time. It indicates membrane fouling and cake layer formation at the boundary. A steady flux of 2-2.5 LMH was obtained after 1h of filtration. The permeate flux shows decreased water flux after hydraulic cleaning at different mass concentration factor (MCF). Thus, hydraulic cleaning did not improve the water flux at different MCF (1-5). The overall recovery of protein (P) and carbohydrate (C) at different stages of UF-NF filtration is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Recovery of whey protein and carbohydrate in integrated membrane processes.

Conclusions: Complete recovery of protein and carbohydrate from whey water was obtained in UF-NF process. The UF-NF showed higher water flux (2.5 LMH), compared to NF-RO reported (1-1.5 LMH). The recovered protein and carbohydrate may be used to make different products (e.g confectionery, dietetic food, infant formula, pharmaceuticals).

Keywords: *Whey water, Recovery, Protein & Carbohydrate, Membrane Processes*

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